

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract. This article gives you a brief overview on how to teach English quickly and easily in elementary school. In this article, you can learn about meaningful and fun ways to teach English to children.

Keywords: elementary, English, children, teaching, fun, song, action, explanation, quick and easy, young children, mental, physical, teacher, voices.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the process of globalization in the world requires people to learn several foreign languages in addition to their native language. Currently, research shows that starting this process at an early age is effective. In our country, serious attention is paid to this issue, and programs are being developed in cooperation with leading organizations and universities in the world based on a new approach to teaching foreign languages, in particular English. This article discusses ideas on teaching foreign languages, in particular English, to children of primary school age. Over the past few years, learning a foreign language has become not only a way of self-development, but also a necessity. A foreign language has become a mandatory component of education not only in schools and universities, but also in many additional preschool educational institutions.

Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, there is a high demand for language learning. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. People first acquire such knowledge in preschool institutions and schools, then in institutes, training courses or independently learn a foreign language. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and qualifications of teachers. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new material. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In teaching English, step-by-step teaching, based on the learner's potential, level, and age, gives good results. Psychologists believe that children learn the language faster and easier than adults.

A child who comes to school for the first time does not fully understand the essence and task of his activity, but he knows that everyone should go to school. Following the instructions of adults, he diligently engages in training. After a certain time, as the impression of joyful moments diminishes, the external signs of school lose their importance, and the child realizes that studying is a daily mental work. In this case, if the child does not have the skills of intellectual work, he will be discouraged from studying, he will feel hopeless, and in order to prevent such a situation, the teacher should inform the child about the difference between education and play, the fun, demonstrate it in practice, and prepare him for this activity. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults.

It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of teaching a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest. Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible.

The following methods can be used to teach children English in a meaningful and interesting way: - through songs and poems that are difficult to explain or remember, have no meaning; - teaching letters or combinations to a tune. - For example, it can be shown that children's learning of the English alphabet by singing is more effective than just memorizing it. - games related to mental and physical activities; - cartoons; While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language. - role play, the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: one student shows howling of a dog and meowing of a cat, another student can show which animal these sounds are. - subject environment; Children learn the language better if the teacher can create that environment depending on the topic.

For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc. On the topic of traveling, the teacher will provide information on the importance of organizing a trip, what means of travel (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA). This situation strengthens students' vocabulary, language abilities, and expands their worldview. There are many more convenient ways to learn English in elementary grades. In addition, these methods should be adapted to the individuality and specific abilities of students.

The following methods are widely studied:

We know that children are curious. They quickly get bored with the sameness. Therefore, it is necessary to change and update the lessons, not always using the same methods. Otherwise, children will understand how the teacher teaches the lesson and prepare for it. Updating the methods increases children's aspirations. How children study at school, how they develop with high goals, largely depends on the family environment, neighborhood attention, and education in a preschool educational institution. The scientific observations and studies presented in the article show that the fact that 70% of all the information a person receives throughout his life is received during his youth indicates how important it is for the development of a child's personality.

So it is not for nothing that the knowledge that children learn in their early years is "engraved in stone", as our ancestors used to say. From this perspective, teaching foreign languages to children at an early age also contributes to the easy acquisition of language skills and competencies. Especially if these knowledge, skills, and competencies are absorbed through various games and educational activities, the child will develop foreign languages as naturally as his native language.

Educational games not only form knowledge, skills, and competencies in a child, but also ensure the child's healthy physical development, refresh him spiritually, strengthen his self-confidence, and greatly contribute to the formation of social relationships with those around him.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, teaching a language to young children should be carried out not as an obligation, but as an interesting activity, and using several effective methods to teach can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. The main task of primary school education is to teach students to “read”, to gain knowledge. Under the influence of education, serious changes occur in the psychological development of children of primary school age. These changes prepare them for the transition to adolescence, which is a responsible period of their lives.

It is necessary to correctly explain to children the importance of learning foreign languages through natural conditions. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr Al-Farabi also knew many foreign languages perfectly, could speak them fluently and created in these languages. Such an opportunity motivated the scientist to study world science and accomplish great things. After all, as our grandfather Navoi said, “He who knows the language knows the people.”

Sources and references used

1. John Adams | Analysis of retirement age in different countries of the world. London 2017.
2. Chet tillarni o'rganish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora –tadbirlari to'g'risida (PQ-1875-son) | Xalq so'zi gazetasi. 2012yil. 12-dekabr.
3. J. Jalolov . —ingliz tilini o'qitish metodlaril —O'qituvchil nashiryoti Toshkent